

Systematic review of value types in academic literature

Analysis on three environmental value types¹

The analysis of results focuses chiefly on a qualitative interpretation of the papers collected according to the interpretation code. The Analysis that follows refers eminently to the use of the three value types introduced in the IPBES Global Assessment (intrinsic, instrumental, and relational) as they appear verbatim or that are identifiable through the common interpretation codes; in the analysis salient associations of these value types with worldviews and policy use/ relevance for policy are also considered.

1. Summary of salient definitions & relevant associations

The summary table below is based on frequency of term(s) exemplifying definition and qualitative interpretation of definition relevance (with respect to assessment statements or through cross-reference with other papers – interpretation based on expert knowledge) – the term *nature is written with an asterisk to highlight that it is not necessarily the word adopted by the papers we analyse, but for the sake of brevity here we use it. In the table additional references from the ILK literature review that are relevant for the environmental value types are added. A more comprehensive merging of different literature searches will be accomplished for the final report.

Table 1. Salient definitions and relevant associations

Value Type	Salient Definitions & relevant associations
Intrinsic Value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Defined negatively as non-instrumental value (i.a. 36;40;41;94; 217; 269; 271; 273; 278) ii. Value of something that is an end-in-itself, agency (i.a. 12, 49, 219, 118, 173, 170, 163, 169, 236; 241; 250; 251; 261) iii. Value independent of being valued or recognized by (human) valuer – inherent properties of an entity (i.a. 30, 51, 67, 78, 95, 114, 123, 128, 130, 237; 275) iv. Regardless of importance and/or usefulness to humans (i.a. 7, 12, 20, 31, 99, 134, 127, 176, 205, 211; 241; 251) v. Inherent moral value of natural entities (teleological centers of life, ends in themselves; valuable for their own sake; right to live/exist) (i.a. 3, 20, 23, 74, 82, 102, 217, 214; 233; 235; 243; 261) - vi. Subjective intrinsic (value of something for its own sake such as aesthetic values, 240; 256;262)
Association worldviews/ values with: broad	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Strongly and explicitly associated with non-anthropocentric, biocentric or ecocentric worldviews (both in the strict sense of moral consideration and in the general sense of an attitude of respect for all life) (i.a. 34, 69, 91, 100, 119, 153, 160; 247; 270; 272) ii. Weakly associated with biospheric, other-regarding, sacred values (146, 181) iii. moral obligations towards natural entities (animals, species, living beings, life in

¹ Numbers in parenthesis correspond to ID numbers in file (B) from the Systematic review of value types (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4396289>).

		general, ecosystems) (107, 117, 201, 210, 217, 211)
Relational Value		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Values of (desirable) human relationships with ‘nature’ (often specified as a particular landscape, place, species, forest etc.) and/or other people/ in the community in which the relationships are embedded (i.a. 4, 30, 140, ILK#112, 173; 239; 279) ii. Values relative to/deriving from meaningful, just, and reciprocal relationships with human and nonhuman beings (i.a. 253; . iii. Values relative to/deriving from relationships that are constituent parts of cultural and/or individual and collective/communal identity (i.a. 69, 177, 196, 189, 231; ILK# 24; 45; 165; 261; 4; 265; 106) iv. Values relative to/deriving from relationships that are constituent elements for living a good life (i.a. 163, 43, 95, 136; ILK# 9, 52; 236; 250) v. Values associated strongly with stewardship and responsibility towards other beings (i.a. 170, 105, 118, 196, 227; 235); care for/about environment, specific landscapes, places, human and nonhuman others (i.a. 143, 154, 227; ILK# 24; 52; 106; 271; 170; 235); sense of place (i.a. 11; 64; 177; 250) , interconnection with cultural and sacred landscape (ILK # 92; 98; 126 Lummi Annex) vi. Strongly associated with cultural ecosystem services vii. Strongly associated with spiritual values viii. Value of *nature as a point of connection among people, binding communities together & supporting social networks (i.a. 196, 97, 188, 177; 250; ILK# 9; 62)
Association with: worldviews/ broad values		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Associated with different worldviews in terms of relational ontologies/epistemologies/ anthropology: beyond separation between nature and culture/society/humanity; biophilia; harmony with nature; relationality and interdependence of all things (non-Western as in Buddhism or Western as in Gaia-Hypothesis or system theories); Natures stewards or caretakers of nature/creation (non-Western and Western as in Genesis 2:15). Very strongly associated with relational, pluricentric or non centric worldviews that question the strict separation between nature and culture/society/humanity and stress the interdependence between all beings (68; 106; 181; 236). ii. Very strongly associated with broad values (general guiding principles or life goals) such as: stewardship, responsibility, care, affection, reciprocity, harmony with nature, good life, justice (ILK# 100; 65; 112). Particularly relevant the (modified) definition by Chan et al. in a broad sense: “preferences, principles, and virtues’ associated with meaningful, reciprocal, and just human–nature relationships”. Kinship (225) iii. Strongly associated with cultural ecosystem services, as well as with religion traditions as spiritual values (ILK# 90; 117; 122; 126; 165; 162, 188)
Instrumental Values		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Means to an external end (where end is mostly intended as usefulness for humans /human use, utility, or benefits) (7, 30, 36, 99, 109, 114, 140, 146, 173, 219, 97; 239; 250) ii. Leading to satisfaction of needs, preferences, interests, and (human) desires (3, 95, 134, 149, 186, 201, 206; 270) iii. Strongly associated with or synonymous to ecosystem services (241; 248; 251). Strongly associated with nature as resource, property, or capital; with other economic values (direct/ indirect use; other TEV categories 233; 278; 282); and with monetary consideration (WtP, PES...) of nature (12, 18, 19, 20, 23, 26, 76, 78, 116, 123, 169, 182, 235; 261)
Association with: worldviews/ broad values		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Very strongly and explicitly associated with anthropocentric (12, 91, 102, 119, 130, 153, 157, 219; 247) ii. Strongly and explicitly associated with utilitarian (direct and indirect use) & associated with mercantilism, managerialism, capitalism (3, 34, 82, 84, 99, 205; 267; 271; 272; 279)

Cross-Cutting themes, such as the values of life-supporting, life-giving, and life-regenerating processes (foundational or fundamental values):

- as intrinsic: 3, 92, 118, 153, 223; 248; 270
- as instrumental: 223; 256; 283
- as relational: 227; 239; 124;
- as separate category (ecological): 187

2. Summary of overlapping meanings and uses across different value types

2.1 Implicit references to values belonging to the semantic field of relational values

Regardless of the specific terminology use with respect to value types there is a large consensus in the literature that *care about and for *nature (mostly specified), responsibility, identity, and sense of place* are essential elements to understand how/why people express/articulate the importance of *nature for them. Although relational values are a recent category used explicitly in the context of environmental values, they are not new with respect to the content they express. Older papers – published before the current terminology of relational values was generally established (before 2016) – and some recent papers, which adopt the old twofold categorization of environmental values, articulate the importance of identity (individual and collective), care about and caring for, sense of place, stewardship, and emotional attachment to the land/ forest/ landscape without using explicitly the term ‘relational value’ or referring to it. In a large number of papers analyzed the value of *nature is incomplete without consideration of these categories, although only more recent publications explicitly refer to them in terms of relational values. These components of the values of *nature are sometimes articulated with respect to very specific aspects of the natural world or NCPs and sometimes in terms of general attitudes or paradigms such as care, stewardship or respect toward *nature in the broadest sense.

Papers implicitly referring to the semantic field of relational values repeatedly use the following approaches/ terminology:

a) the term *intrinsic value* is used as an overarching concept defined negatively against instrumental values, not as a means to an end or in the sense of value for its own sake (sometimes called subjective intrinsic value). A representative number of papers lump aesthetic appreciation (f.ex. #240), contemplation, identity-constitutive values or place attachment with intrinsic value.

b) attitudes, practices or paradigms of respect, care, stewardship, and responsibility toward *nature are often represented in terms of *broad values* (general guidance principles, or norms).

c) in a significantly smaller number of papers the use and definition of *instrumental values* is broadened to include, for example, non-economic values (aesthetic, spiritual), functional values (indirect, not merely means), or values related to health (one paper lists under instrumental values activities in green

spaces that produce “physical, psychological, emotional, social, cognitive-educational, social and labour-integration benefits” for people), or to non-economic recreation.

The majority of papers highlights the importance of values, which can be situated in the semantic field of relational values, as *non-instrumental* and, in absence of an alternative term, tend to frame them in the language of intrinsic value, including the beauty of a landscape for local people or the meaning of a place for the identity of a local community. Some papers state that relational values were previously framed as instrumental values (in TEEB or in the MEA), but this is not a prevalent position in the literature. The reference is likely due to the fact that cultural ecosystem services are framed as in the domain of relational, non-instrumental values and in the literature a strong association (often to the point of alleged synonymity) can be found between instrumental values and the ecosystem services framework.

2.1.1 Synthesis of implicit use of values belonging to the semantic field or domain of relational values

Within the domain of relational values, amenities and recreational services overlap more easily with instrumental values and are more often mentioned in papers referring to economic valuation (TEV for example); identity-constitution, sense of place, spiritual values overlap mostly with (subjective) intrinsic values and are clearly framed as non-instrumental and, with some exception, outside of the domain of economic valuation; aesthetic values appear more often in both domains, intrinsic and instrumental, albeit with higher salience under the domain of intrinsic value.

Detailed example aesthetic values:

Aesthetic values are sometimes intended as intrinsic (something is aesthetically valuable for its own sake, regardless of usefulness or utility) and sometimes as instrumental (something is aesthetically valuable because it causes aesthetic pleasure, intended as satisfaction of preference, interest, or desire). In papers explicitly using the relational value concept, aesthetic values are defined as relational and non-instrumental (aesthetic appreciation or experience as essential component of a good life). This example can be used to show possible overlapping area across value types – an overlapping that can be useful for policy interventions in sense that, regardless of the way in which different people/ social groups/ stakeholders express why/how they value biodiversity or NCP aesthetically, there can be convergence on some dimensions and motivations that can be mobilized for environmental policies or assessed to better frame and understand lines of conflicts or of possible convergence across social actors.²

² **Interpretation for a possible example to elaborate on:** ‘beauty’ or ‘aesthetic value’ of *nature that appears under all value types. This is why it is intended and framed differently. In terms of intrinsic value the beauty of ‘nature’, say a forest, is valuable for its own sake regardless and independently of usefulness (beauty is not considered in terms of preference or utility) and it is non-negotiable. In terms of instrumental value, beauty is conceived as a preference for a beautiful state of affairs over a different less beautiful state and can be expressed as willingness to pay, i.e. via hedonic valuation (value of real estate in the vicinity of ‘beautiful’ green areas). In

2.2. Fuzzy boundaries and overlaps between intrinsic and instrumental values

Intrinsic and Instrumental values are mostly presented as a clear dichotomy, but there are contested or poorly articulated “fuzzy” areas between the two value types in the literature. These include: non-use values, aesthetic and spiritual values, sense of awe and beauty toward nature, place attachment, constitutive identity associated with nature or place, and the function of life sustaining systems.

These “fuzzy areas” are sometimes inconsistently attributed. For example, life-sustaining systems are intended a) as ecosystem functions in the domain of instrumental values or b) as biophysical characteristics of entities, regardless of benefits to people, in the domain of intrinsic values. Whereas ecosystem services mostly fall under the domain of instrumental values, biodiversity is more often associated with intrinsic values. This inconsistency depends on how stretched/broad the definition of each type of value is intended in the paper. However, these ‘fuzzy’ understandings rarely mesh with the more consistently widespread definitions of these two value types as presented above and/or often with the definitions of intrinsic and instrumental values used within the same paper.

Another overlapping area between intrinsic and instrumental values is the category of instrumental values in the sense of importance and benefits to non-human entities and processes. This meaning does not appear often in the literature, but is used to refer to a) ecosystem functions that do not directly lead to services for humans and/or b) indirect moral obligations regarding environmental conditions that are necessary for the survival of – for example – sentient animals.

2.3 Relational Values and Contextual NCP

terms of relational value, beauty is understood as a relation to a specific place, landscape, ecosystem and/or species that deeply informs the identity of an individual/community and its sense of belonging and/or shapes an individual/community’s willingness to care for that place (etc.). In the relational sense, articulating beauty in terms of trade-offs or preferences is firmly resisted. . Regardless of the perspective taken, a specific place/ecosystem/landscape is considered beautiful by different groups of people for different reasons. Depending on the context, it might be relevant or not to know more details about the different reasons and motivations that people express or embody when considering something beautiful/ or having aesthetic value (or not). It might be relevant for example for policy interventions that rely on a community’s engagement and collaboration in the preservation of an area. Or, as in the case of wetland restoration in North-east Germany, to transform positively people’s attitudes towards wetlands – which were considered under the GDR regime as useless and fastidious areas obstructing agricultural production. The aesthetic values of wetlands can be ignited through environmental education interventions, projects in collaboration with schools, excursions to learn about biodiversity and to connect with the wetlands, through exchange and communication between different groups of people, or via recreational access, shared and sustainable use (for cattle), etc. Different reasons for the beauty of restored wetlands can meet and sustain positive attitudes of care towards them.

Continuing with the wetland example, making explicit different types of value of wetlands would appeal to different people – the consideration of plural values could lead to a wider support for the intervention and reduce local conflicts: wetlands have instrumental value (carbon sequestration), intrinsic value from the point of view of many ecologists studying the high diversity of living forms that has a right to live and flourish, and relational values for those who consider them an essential component for the life of the community, something to care for, or a beautiful landscape beyond any trade-off (REF to be added about restoring the relationships to wetlands).

As specific values, relational values are framed in a large number of papers as context dependent/specific, non-transferable, non-tradable, and non-substitutable. They can help articulate the idea that a specific place, a tree, an animal – or a population are essentially important to people (individuals or communities) because of the unique relationship or history they have with it.

In most cases, relational values (whether explicitly addressed using this term or by considering within another value domain), when not used to express broad values, tend to be more significantly context-related than intrinsic or instrumental values and refer to relationships between people and nature in specific socio-cultural circumstances and often in particular geographies and spatial-temporal circumstances. Instrumental values are often referred to specific ecosystem services broadly ('carbon sequestration') are more generalizable and can often be separated from the specific ecosystem where they are generated. Similarly, intrinsic values often refer to general categories of beings (sentient animals, living beings, species). In comparably more cases relational values, instead, refer to particular animals, places, landscapes, relationships, although there are also several papers that theorize them more generally. To use IPBES language, RV seem to account better for contextual NCP. (Interpretation: in cases where the concept of RV is not explicitly used contextual NCPs tend to be handled awkwardly or inconsistently, whereas explicitly using relational values more adequately address contextual NCPs and allows their importance to be communicated more clearly and with less confusion.)

3. Summary of other relevant findings

3.1 General Findings and literature gaps

Relevant findings from the qualitative interpretation of the results are listed below. The order does not refer to any priority and is random.

- i. Ecosystem services very frequently equated to Instrumental values.³
- ii. Ecocentric/biocentric worldviews are almost exclusively associated with intrinsic values, whereas relational values are associated with relational, non-centric/ pluricentric worldviews, and non-dichotomic perspectives.
- iii. A large number of papers highlights the importance of people' motivations to conserve nature and articulates the role that assessing values plays for this reason. This suggests an undercurrent of unexpressed normative assumptions that conserving nature is important, more or less along the lines "we don't care/ do not address why conserving nature is important, but we need to find the "why" that will convince people to do it."
- iv. Religious interpretations (both in the case of Easterns and Western religions) engage with value types in various ways. Several papers on/from Chinese perspectives frame the intrinsic value language as rooted in Western traditions and in human-nature separation.

³ This general understanding seems to play a role in justifying the need for introducing NCP to widen the perspective of ecosystem services narrowly intended and to include other value types.

- v. In some paper the term *instrumental values* is associated with ecological function in general, even if not with respect to usefulness to humans
- vi. Oftentimes the term *intrinsic value* is associated with 'existence value' but not intended in economic terms, rather as right to exist for one's own sake. The term is mostly not used in association to the (Total Economic Value) TEV or any other economic literature but could be a point of confusion or contention in interdisciplinary work.
- vii. The paradigm of conservation seems to be getting twisted into biodiversity vs. ecosystem services corresponding to the intrinsic/instrumental dichotomy, with only few, tenuous, attempts to bridge. Biodiversity is framed as something that should be protected for its own sake whereas ecosystem services stress benefits to humans. *Interpretation and literature gap*: It would be interesting to explore how/whether the relational value domain can help bridging between these categories (for example via the ES cascade, via the idea of complex social-ecological systems, through the concept of biocultural diversity, or via non-material and contextual NCP).
- viii. The overlapping field of what we can call for operational reasons life-support values is underrepresented in the literature. *Interpretation/ identification of literature gap*: This overlapping field might need to be re-evaluated or explored further. It covers the overlapping area between the intrinsic and the instrumental domain of ecosystem functions that do not lead directly to services or benefits to humans, but constitute fundamental conditions for life.
- ix. In the relational values domain, *eudaemonic* (referring to a good and flourishing life) and *constitutive* (that make up individual and collective identity) relational values can be situated along the two opposite of a continuous spectrum: constitutive RV are closer to (subjective) intrinsic values whereas eudaemonic are partially closer to instrumental values (recreational, amenity). The position on the spectrum depends on how they are actually articulated and framed by people or by assessment designers (as essential components of a good life or as preference satisfaction in a utilitarian framework).
- x. Instrumental values mostly fall under the domain of economics or economic valuation. This is less clear with other value types. From the relational value domain it is mostly aesthetic, recreational, health-related values that are associated with economic perspectives. The majority of papers are critical of purely economic approaches. Even when defending instrumental values as easier to implement in policy, several papers stress the wide range of these values, which are not merely market-based.
- xi. In the dichotomy between biodiversity/ecosystem services or intrinsic/instrumental, each 'camp' argues that the other one has been dominant in the last 20 years and that it has not been successful for implementing conservation. On the one hand, the ecosystem services paradigm is presented as a re-enactment of a merely

instrumental, economic, and anthropocentric consideration of nature as resource. A change of paradigm towards biocentric and ecocentric worldviews is deemed necessary for successful policies for conservation and to enhance people's motivation. On the other hand, the ecosystem services paradigm is presented as innovation with respect to the 'old' conservation paradigm rooted in the intrinsic value of nature independently of usefulness to humans. The instrumental approach would offer a wider basis for consensus and be more attractive for a sustainable path. Intrinsic value is considered as not assessable and therefore difficult to implement. Accordingly, the instrumental perspective is more pragmatic.

The dichotomy also runs through a normative clash between a deontological approach (obligations towards nature rooted in moral norms, worldviews, and principles) versus a consequentialist/ utilitarian approach (guiding principles is utility and what should be done depends on the consequences of actions/inaction and not on general norms). Relational values and the NCP paradigm may be able to bridge the gap between approaches.

3.2 Policy-relevant findings

In the following general statements from the literature are summarized without detailed analysis. The order does not refer to any priority and is random.

- i. Plural Values support better and more successful policies for conservation. Understanding people's interaction with *nature enable more effective communication; non-tangible costs and benefits/ non-quantifiable aspects can be highlighted; considering pluralistic values leads to more equitable & effective/ inclusive & just outcomes; reduces/facilitates understanding of conflicts and represent better different interests; fosters co-management; reduces risk of crowding out other motivations; helps building common ground across different stakeholders by acknowledging different reasons and motivations.
- ii. Plural Valuation is essential for policy to reflect the plurality of people's values. Monistic approaches are less relevant for all stakeholders.
- iii. Relational Values can support environmental policy. RV can be catalysts for motivation; can speak to a broader audience, including experts and policy makers; not considering them can jeopardize food sovereignty, impact identity and decline attachment to place (for farmers); support sense of responsibility; more powerful leverage for conservation; more contextual; increase participation; support environmental education; too vague to be useful for implementation and overlap with other value types; elicit reciprocity; policy targeted towards the web of relations which exist between mind, body, culture and the environment are recommended.

- iv. Instrumental Values are important, but better if complemented by others. They are more pragmatic; they focus on the utility of biodiversity to humans and make intervention easier; narrow focus leads to more exploitation.
- v. Intrinsic values are essential for people, but might lack a pragmatic dimension. They are considered essential for environmental education; they are very meaningful to people; they might lead to unacceptable outcomes. Ecocentric education increases pro-environmental behavior; speaking only of ES can alienate stakeholders who frame HNR differently.
- vi. Understanding motivation & behavior is important for policy interventions. Documenting the relationship between values and preferences can help understand communities' aspirations regarding environmental management.
- vii. Participation is important for successful policy.
- viii. Convergence. Agreement on best practices can occur across different value types. One interesting paper proposes three paradigms as convergence paths: a) breath of human values (Norton's convergence hypothesis that calls for intergenerational morality and considered preferences (weak anthropocentrism) as mediation; b) Constant Natural Capital Rule as mediation between weak and strong sustainability - to be protected for different reasons (intrinsic or instrumental/relational); c) precautionary principle as mediation between techno-optimists and techno-pessimists (interpretation, 233).

4. Detailed presentation of results

In the following section more detailed paraphrases or direct quotations from papers are listed and thematically grouped.

4.1 Policy relevance

Plural values and plural valuation

1. Paper 234 proposes convergence of the three paradigms/ value types for policy: a) breath of human values (Norton's convergence hypothesis that calls for intergenerational morality and considered preferences (weak anthropocentrism) as mediation; b) Constant Natural Capital Rule as mediation between weak and strong sustainability - to be protected for different reasons (intrinsic or instrumental/relational); c) precautionary principle as mediation between techno-optimists and techno-pessimists (interpretation, 234).
2. Characterizing values as simply instrumental and/or intrinsic inherently separates humans and biodiversity from the processes of agricultural production, and can lead to "one-size-fits-all" policies (4).

3. Argue that multiple values of ecosystems expressed by rural and urban societies should be included in environmental management to tackle social conflicts and consider the diverse needs and interests of different social actors (interpretation of 7).
4. "stakeholders do have a variety of reasons for why nature should be conserved, ranging from moral to more anthropocentric and utilitarian arguments, there is an overall appreciation of certain aspects of the intrinsic value of nature. This, and the existence of elements of utilitarian or anthropocentric perspectives in all groups provides, some common ground with opportunities for building an inclusive discourse around biodiversity conservation (20)."
5. Sorts different values/worldviews into "images". These can explain conflicts, disagreements, and opposition to interventions and managers/decision makers can use this tool to tweak interventions to make them more in line with the concerns, views, and values of those affected by interventions (interpretation of 34).
6. Finding an appropriate language for the value of nature has policy ramifications (interpretation of 41). ; The paper argues for the benefits of relational values, among other things in real world decision making. An important reason is the concept allows for folding into the decision making process more diverse social science perspectives (beyond economics) (interpretation, 45).
7. Policy relevance flows from improving value assessments. It is the purpose of IPBES to support decision-making (interpretation 51).
8. The view seems to be that instrumental values guide policy making although other, and unspecified, values are what sets the goals and aims (conservation in this case) (interpretation, 58).
9. "Furthermore, stakeholders' re- presentations of nature regarding both cultural and regulating benefits obtained from nature are not converging with traditional ES classifications. This has implications for the employment of the ES concept and classical ES classifications in science-practice-policy processes. We warn against applying the standard theoretical ES concept when this is not congruent with stakeholders' representations of nature (65)."
10. "Additionally, in our review, we found little empirically based research on the link between human–nature relationships and landscape management and none on the role of activation or how HNRs catalyze behavior. Before we have a better understanding of these interconnections, landscape and natural resource managers might be advised to be aware that the ES concept dominating contemporary environmental management policy and practice may only cover a narrow segment of the broad human–nature relationship spectrum (85)."
11. "aesthetic experience is informed by values, particularly use/intrinsic values for nature, and in turn influences acceptability judgments mainly by influencing beliefs about consequences for the natural environment (87)."

12. Claim: theoretical controversy between maximization of ecosystem services (instrumental values) & biodiversity conservation (intrinsic value) partially align in policy - each goal also reaches to a certain percentage the other goal in the scenario model (between 47 and 70 percent) (interpretation, 212).
13. "it requires a new understanding of ecosystem services which recognises the importance of reciprocal social relations between diverse individuals and groups, including between indigenous and non-indigenous people (Jackson and Palmer 2015)." The model can also be applied to environmental managers: "we recommend that environmental management plans be targeted at the web of relations which exist between mind, body, culture and the environment. There are two potential ways of managing such webs of relations: (1) revise them after they collapse by encouraging the actualisation of new affordances in the landscape, and (2) design or implement environmental management plans for both emergent and collapsing relations from the outset.(from 215)" ;
14. "bottom-up processes are more likely to foster learning among participants and those in their social network, because they take a pluralist approach which seeks and values all perspectives on the conflict (216).
15. Moving beyond either biodiversity (intrinsic value) or ES (instrumental value) can be beneficial in some cases from the point of view of policy. Both approaches have to be interpreted in a non-narrow sense & specific, contextual conditions for win-win, win-lose. and win-neutral situations have to be identified in policy. For potential win-win cases, broad alliances are possible (interpretation, 219).
16. Monism (monetary incentives) crowd out intrinsic reasons for protecting biodiversity (interpretation, 221).
17. "need to move from language of rights to language of global responsibilities that go beyond national borders. "Regionalism in environmental policy can be a good thing, but only if the regional focus is as geographical and ecological as it is political, and only if the region knows its global connections (223)."
18. "following Norton, the paper argues unity in policy can be reached from different position in environmentalism: "environmentalists may consistently disagree over the reasons for a specific policy direction without disagreeing over the policy direction itself." Four convergence concepts are proposed that can support policy pragmatically (interpretation of 233).
19. "The analysis shows that relational values are essential to consider at the science-policy interface as they are an important set of values that people hold about nature and that go beyond instrumental relations (239)."

20. Agrifood and global food trade: "This practice frequently excludes social groups in the respective countries from acquiring benefits from agriculture and experiencing the RV derived from their lands: it not only jeopardizes the dimension of food security and sovereignty by controlling the land, but it also impacts the dimension of identity, heritage and stewardship, by accelerating the decline of farmers' place attachment, the sense of belonging, the local and traditional knowledge (239)".
21. Understanding the values that drive people's interactions with waterways can enable management bodies to communicate more effectively with stakeholders. Illuminating the full range of values associated with a given resource or environment can thus enrich management decision-making processes by bringing into focus the often neglected non-tangible costs and benefits associated with those decisions." (279)
22. "considering such pluralistic values when formulating conservation strategies or interventions might yield outcomes that are more equitable and effective for humans and non-humans alike." (250).
23. "Basing my argument on the premise that no single evaluative model can provide a comprehensive accounting of all environmental values in all situations, I explore a more inclusive viewpoint on which multiple approaches to identifying and measuring environmental values are considered valid." (Norton) 198.
24. Identifying multiple consequences on communities: "the absence of fish resulting from ecological damage affects both food availability and the quality of social connections, which in turn affects individual gender practices and symbolizes genocide to the community" (Noorgard, Klamath River) 196.
25. Truism in decision-making that stakeholders are only motivated by economic gains blinds alternative opportunities for environmental management plans that enhance communication of other values (case study in Argentina) 188.
26. No-net-loss approaches are useful if they capture not only attributes of ecosystems, but also different value types associated with them Sole focus on ES "might hide forms of environmental concern or stewardship that may be an important part of cultural identity." 170.
27. "many aspects of the human connection with nature are unquantifiable and are not amenable to trade-offs with any kind of material benefit; many environmental practices are highly social in nature, rendering inadequate the notion of an economic exchange among individuals as a basis for evaluating those practices; and, finally, many cultures and individuals consider nature to evince many other values than utilitarian ones" 165.
28. Considering a plurality of values in policy and management decisions making will facilitate value articulation that is more inclusive and just 124.

29. Including diversity of users perception reduce conflict by fostering co-management in protected areas 96.
30. "To facilitate managers' consideration of potential power imbalances and tradeoffs amongst groups [...] it has explored whether understanding the users' value assignments can facilitate better understanding of potential conflict" AND: "The ways in which the intrinsic, instrumental and relational value categories manifest within the cluster groups provide a new option for stakeholder segmentation that could help managers to avoid conflicts related with potential power imbalances or trade-off" 95 (Chile).
31. Improve effects of policy intervention and involvement of local communities: "One complicating factor is that funding providers and policy makers tend to have a different interpretation of the benefits provided by ecosystems than rural Malagasy people. Policy makers, for example, focus on protecting forests in order to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, whereas local people see the forest as being essential for their dietary requirements and their health, and as a resting place for their ancestors." 92.
32. Importance of plural valuation for policy to mirror the plurality of values - Policy will be better informed with pluralistic valuations of ecosystem services. Single value assessments are often ignored because they are not relevant for all stake-holders 139.
33. Convergence Hypothesis for policy: instrumental approach can capture intrinsic values indirectly (intergenerational justice) 198; What we really need to bring forward the usability and relevance of the concept and operationalise its mainstreaming in planning and policy consulting are, therefore, agreements on best practices in assessments. These should ensure that all aspects of nature and its values – intrinsic ones and those with directly measurable benefits for human well-being – are equally and sufficiently considered 94.
34. Education and information impact positively pro-environmental behaviour and norm activation in moral reasoning 166.
35. Educating to ecocentrism (intrinsic value) increases pro-environmental attitude and has instrumental value for humanity 130.
36. Considering and accommodating religious perspectives enhances chances of acceptability of environmental interventions 129.

Relational Values:

1. "The landscape of any farm is the owner's portrait of himself (4)."
2. "Once we recognize that value is experienced via relationship, it becomes clear that various types of human relationship with nature, which Chan et al. (2016) call "relational values," are experiential analogues to the philosophical notion of subjective [intrinsic values] (13)."

3. Understanding relational values are useful for waterways management because they are specifically about the human-nature connections and unlike the stable held values, can change more readily in response to positive or negative experiences. (279).
4. These relational values have been identified as catalysts to motivate landscape stewardship among local stakeholders (Lynham et al. 2017, Peçanha Enqvist et al. 2018, West et al. 2018).” (276); “the emerging idea of ‘relational values’ has the potential to significantly influence policies as well as concrete management... it carries the capacity to speak into the broad audience of experts and policy makers with value-oriented perspectives” (253).
5. Essential role of RV (in a gradient with instrumental and intrinsic) for science-policy interface. Development of indicators and proxies to measure them: "The analysis shows that relational values are essential to consider at the science-policy interface as they are an important set of values that people hold about nature and that go beyond instrumental relations." (239).
6. With reference to agrifood: "This practice frequently excludes social groups in the respective countries from acquiring benefits from agriculture and experiencing the RV derived from their lands: it not only jeopardizes the dimension of food security and sovereignty by controlling the land, but it also impacts the dimension of identity, heritage and stewardship, by accelerating the decline of farmers’ place attachment, the sense of belonging, the local and traditional knowledge” 239.
7. Important to support sense of responsibility towards nature: “"By institutionalizing the fact that nature can be destroyed as long as the destruction is compensated, we ruin the special sense of responsibility that has been so hard to mainstream." 187.
8. "Framing conservation with relational values may offer more powerful leverage for conservation than emphasis on instrumental or intrinsic values” - evidence in support of RV for policy making, in particular with respect to International Union for Conservation of Nature's Key Biodiversity Areas partnership - stressing partnership with nature that resonates with people locally can enhance motivation for conservation. RV are more contextual and can help operationalize IPBES regionally.
9. Importance of enhancing RV by increasing participation and reducing exclusion (on race-base for example) 162.
10. “Taking a care perspective would help shift the focus from the abstract notion of what people value, which per se does not provide very clear implications as to how nature is to be used or conserved (e.g. wilderness vs managed conservation), to a practice-oriented level of caring for. What someone cares for, how and why, provides a much more tangible entry point as to how an area is to be used or not, what practices are acceptable to different groups etc. So the main benefit of the care concept for conservation practice may lie in asking the right questions rather than providing pro-conservation answers.” 143.

11. "Value articulation frameworks that do not consider relational values ignore historic power imbalances between different cultural views of human nature relationships, hiding underlying social power relations" 124.
12. Essential to capture ILK perspectives "fostering a greater diversity of relational-based environmental values" can improve environmental education - governance practices can support these relationships 104.
13. Relational values lit, post Chan et al., 2016, has a central focus on old dichotomy of values, old conception of ES, old PES, etc. obscuring the range of values that are relevant to people and nature. Relational values help minimize this. Relational values can minimize or resolve conflicts.

Instrumental values:

1. 88% of 1582 papers reviewed in (8) used only instrumental measurements, the review focused on restoration ecology.
2. "Market-based instruments that often involve the commodification of ecosystem services (Deliege and Neuteleers, 2015) are fast becoming the policy instruments of choice for biodiversity management around the world (17)."
3. Instrumental values equated with ecological perspective of ecosystem functions (network/ web of life). Interesting because conservationists would reject this interpretation (interpretation of 225).
4. Important to assess ES, but better considering other values as well for conservation. Only aspect of biodiversity that deliver utility to humans should be considered for conservation.
5. Only focusing on protecting the Earth for human interests leads to more exploitation 118.
6. It makes more sense for Instrumental arguments to be made as the basis of nature conservation 99.

Intrinsic values:

1. "nature working as it is; species are the product of a long history of continuing evolution by means of ecological processes, and so they have the right to continued existence life forms should be conserved simply because they exist: they are the product of a long history of continuing evolution by means of ecological processes, and so they have the right to a continued existence (3).
2. Postulations of (intrinsic) value to non-human nature do not seem to be indispensable to environmental ethics (interpretation from 16).

3. Lack of consideration of pragmatic elements relevant to environmental policy (184).
4. European conservation areas: in addition to intrinsic values that were the original basis of setting aside natural reserves, instrumental values of these areas must and are now being considered 147.
5. Importance of intrinsic value in education in order to support human life in the face of environmental crisis.
6. Without intrinsic values argument for conservation rely on scientific proof of dependence upon ecosystem functions
7. Policies based on intrinsic values might lead to unacceptable outcomes (ecotax on tourism).
8. Policies based on intrinsic values are necessary to avoid tragedy of the commons.
9. Against the assumption that the poor would align mostly with instrumental values: The paper demonstrates that even in a relatively low-income community in the Philippines, intrinsic values were quite meaningful to people - by appealing to them policies are more successful.

4.2 A better understanding of behaviour

1. "However, in almost all cases, only the proximal factors are considered in shaping a response, i.e. the direct practices that change biodiversity, not the ultimate causes as how policy drive farmers 'behavior, or how farm structure constraints farmers 'options, or the social consequences of biodiversity management" (15).
2. The paper discusses different 'frames'; attachment, attractiveness, rurality. These concern how people value and think about their environment and affects how they perceive of floodplain restoration (which is what the paper examines) (interpretation of 33).
3. Determining factors such as the ways in which people value natural areas can help in the development of more effective responses to these problems. Documenting the relationships between values and preferences for protection of natural areas, for example, can assist our understanding of community aspirations for natural area management. (278).

4.3 Participatory approaches

1. Looks at different "frames" of nature and how people that can be associated with one frame or another are susceptible to particular arguments for restoration. They content safety based arguments are ineffective and more participation of stakeholders is likely to have benefits (interpretation of 33).

- Approaches that incorporate stakeholders. Environmental Impact Assessments need to do a better and more fair job of involving the public to avoid costs of environmental degradation 144.

4.4 Institutions and Values

- "Management strategies must recognize that PA establishment and management is often a social act that produces changes in an inhabited environment (6)."
- Education and scientific knowledge (taxonomy of insects) are essential to help forming and changing values of relationship to place for example (interpretation of 230).

5. Table with detailed results on specific values (environmental value types)

The following table offers a more detailed overview of terms found in the literature analysis, associations, and correspondence to semantic fields/ meanings. The numbers overlap because the same paper can present various terms, definitions, and associations. The 'i' refer to the strength/ magnitude of the association/ meaning/ definitions. The meanings/associations/definitions are grouped in categories

Table 2 Detailed results of literature search

Intrinsic value			
Definition	Category	Keywords	Count of papers
	non- utilitarian non- instrumental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • non-utilitarian values ii • cost of conserving the environment and resources of a wetland. Include values for biodiversity protection, scientific research, education, cultural services • Non-market values, non economic (intangibles) ii • end-value, referring to what is valuable for its own sake iiiiii • non-instrumental iiiiii - (some go further and say values not included in ecosystem services, 62). • independent of its value or use to any other entity iiiiii • not based on ES functions • regardless of importance utility, interest, or usefulness for humans • non-material benefits • non-use values • regardless of cost they might generate 186 • non-relational - independent of relations to anything else i • Independent of relation to humans: iiiii • non substitutable 	71
	non- anthropocentric worldviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • non-anthropocentric iiiiii • humans are just a part of the "web of life" equal with many other aspects of creation - humans are part of nature iiiiii 	47

	Broad Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ecocentric iiiiiiii ● biocentric worldview iiiiiiii ● altruistic i, other-regarding i ● biospheric i ● theocentric, sacred - value for God (Allah) 129 ● responsibility and care for life in general ● People are motivated by a belief that non-human things are valuable regardless of usefulness to humans: iiiii 	
	inherent moral value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● all forms of life have intrinsic value, moral worth, and the right to self-realization, pursuing a good of one's own, teleological centers of life iiiiiiii ● right to live, exist or survive iiiiiiii ● obligation towards nature, earth, and its elements iiiiiiii ● value in and of itself iiiiiiii (for its own sake) ● moral standing ii ● inherent goodness - of species iii ● animals have subjective consciousness ii and are sacred ● equality of life forms iii ● Intrinsic values belong to things that are able to value: i 	59
	inherent properties of an object	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● inner value of an object in terms of value in itself. iiiii ● qualitative property of an object i (dispositional property that activates valuers)- regardless of recognition by humans (independent of human valuers). iiiiiiii ● 'intrinsic validity' because world-like qualities (e.g., stability, beauty) inhere in them. ● beauty ii ● biophysical characteristics of a natural entity ii ● measurable through exergy ● for what nature is and not for what it does (205) ● ecological value i ● Real values embedded in the environment: i 	28
	existence value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● existence value ii ● humanistic value of nature ● reference to PES: (produces benefits because of its existence, and the knowledge of it is valued by citizens) ● right to exist regardless of humans ● Lifeforms should be conserved simply because they exist because they are products of a long history of evolution: ii ● Animals are evolutionary relatives and thus to some degree comparable to humans with intrinsic value. ● Intrinsically worth protecting ● Existence value: i ● A species/thing has specific value following from its own objective nature ● Irreplaceability 	13
	end in itself	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● iiiiiiii iiiiiiii ● "Nature for its own sake": iiiii 	24

	importance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • life itself at the forefront of consideration • symbolic value (of animals) 	
	positive value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • emotional, moral, aesthetic, and scientific dimensions, often in combination (262) • Ethics founded on respect for nature could be a social mechanism for affirming intrinsic value of ecosystems and limiting their alternation: 	
	Fuzzy areas, overlap with relational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • comprises cultural, social, aesthetic, and ethical benefits. • aesthetic & contemplation iiiii - requires valuing an object in itself • reflect how RV and intrinsic value can coexist (209) • humans are part of the circle of intrinsic values - intrinsic value from the Earth system itself (209) • subjective intrinsic value (200) • "identity-constitutive reasons refer not only to the intrinsic merit of an agent's options, but also to the significance or meaning of an option in terms of the agent's life plan or life story." 189 • constitutive relational values defined as intrinsic value 164 • human attachment to and enduring affinity for these places 162 • ecosystemic and biospheric function i • ability to regenerate ES • cultural attachment to land, influence woodland owners' propensity to sell (19). • Sense of place is important in some "frames" of nature: • Mental state (pleasure, awe)=intrinsic values, this could be a link to relational values. • Use of intrinsic values seems to encompass what other's are calling relational values. 	
	Western concept	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chinese papers contest that intrinsic value is a Western concept rooted in Western Metaphysics (245; 246) 	
	Biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity is a/the intrinsic value of nature: iii • Ecological value: • Biocentric reasoning 	
Interpretations & Questions		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contemplation of nature • independent of place • dualistic (opposition human-nature) • critical of corporate involvement in conservation • The subjective aspect of intrinsic values • Intrinsic values cannot be assessed? • "Clarification of how the viability of economic valuation of intrinsic values relies on whether one bases the idea of intrinsic value on consequentialism or deontological ethics. The conceptualisation of intrinsic value as external to ecosystem services (as per the MEA) relies on deontological ethics, and economic valuation (using the method of benefit transfer) is viable if one relies on consequentialism. (interpretation, 62)" • Intrinsic values included as cultural ecosystem services • Refer to non-use values and option values in the TEV framework as Intrinsic values. 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrinsic values of nature associated closely with aesthetic values come up a couple of times. 	
	source	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • anthropomorphic - brought into nature by human valuers that create worlds (Arendt) (204) • subjective (generated by observer) and objective (resides in entity) intrinsic value (Sandler 2012) ii • subjective value-expressions of objective intrinsic value 	

Instrumental value			
Definition	Category	Keywords	Count of papers
	utilitarian	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilitarian values are divided into direct and indirect utilitarian values. Direct utilitarian values are the values of raw materials that wetlands produce for people's direct consumption such as reeds, lotus roots and fish. Indirect utilitarian values are the values of gas regulation, water supply, water regulation, waste treatment and ecotourism • utilitarian • Utility to non-humans: • Ecosystem functions and support for all living things 	18
	economic natural capital resource	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • means to ends for human benefits i • utility for humans ii • economic benefits. TEV iiiiiiiiiiiiiiiii • use and non-use value (Use values encompass the values humans extract from natural areas (timber, water grazing and so on) as well as on-site activities such as recreation and nature study); non-use: existence value is the benefit received by those who derive satisfaction from knowing that a site is preserved in a certain condition irrespective of use or potential use by the individual or others + 'bequest' to future generations + options values. Non-use/indirect: enjoyment, recreation. iii • Existence value as instrumental (277) • part of commodification of nature (critique) i • value for development • satisfaction of preferences • CBA and price increments, market-based incentives ii • use values • stock of depletable natural capital which must be preserved so that it continues to deliver the resource and its inherent benefits • nature as resource, property, or capital iiiiiiiiiiiii • Economic (direct values are instrumental, indirect, non-use are intrinsic): i • Energy economics (88)? I • Monetary benefits • Commodities: Agricultural/Forest products in raw units or market value: iii 	42
	anthropocent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • anthropocentric iiiiiiiiiiiiiiiiiiiii - qualities of entities and how well they suit 	35

		<p>people 97</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Places are imbued with value which shape right conduct and demand responsibilities toward them (26). 	
	paradigm/ broad value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Western concept ii - development, capitalism • rooted in mercantilism • utilitarian i • Instrumental values are motivation based on self-benefit:i • use and control of nature • managerial approach • Dominant social paradigm (dsp): conmputive, exploitative, growth oriented • Prudence in use of resources 	
Interpretations and questions		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stewardship as use of ES • non-anthropocentric instrumental values (biocentric) 273 • Consumerism • Can include value to future generations 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • substitutable and non substitutable instrumental values (208) 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • help evaluating change according to impacts of changes on human welfare (Norton) 	

Relational value			
Definition	Category	Keywords	Count of papers
	Worldviews: relational anthropologies/ ontologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • human beings are relational ii • no separation between nature and culture iiiiii - “living well” with nature, “biocultural ethics”, spiritual cosmologies, beyond anthropocentrism and human-nature dualism - animism and shamanism: “all living beings share the same culture, whereas their bodies differ according to their ecological behavior” 165 • Biophilia • Relationality of all things (Vedanta, Buddhism) iii • Gaia - complex systems, interrelation of all things • “‘preferences, principles, and virtues’ associated with meaningful, reciprocal, and just human–nature relationships (30)”:iiiiii • “the values that are imbedded in desirable (sought after) relationships, including those among people and between people and nature”: iiiiii • Modes of relation between human and non-human, encompassing expanding web of consequences---social, material and economic, agency of non-human actors as relational (236). • Lifeworld in which humans participate with other creatures (218). • All things are connected in the context of life (comes up a lot but not necessarily attributed to relational values (eg 223)) 	21
	broad values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • held or experiential values 	28

	<p>and attitudes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● harmony with nature iiiii also: tian ren he yi 天人合一, which can be translated as the harmonious relationship between human beings and nature - Daoists' conception of living in harmony with nature is based on aesthetic appreciation and participation in the beauty of nature." 246 ● "In the process of aesthetic appreciation, human beings extend their feelings of social sympathy toward other living beings. Therefore, the process of investigation of things is also the process of aesthetic appreciation through the projection of sympathy. Through sympathy, we feel the happiness and suffering of living beings. Aesthetic appreciation of living beings is ultimately based on our feelings" 245 ● "preferences, principles, and virtues associated with the relationships that people have with components of nature, i.e. when the relationships themselves matter to people, beyond a means to an end." 239 broad or specific? ● Responsibility, care, reciprocity, good life iiiiiiii: core values (universal moral values like care, responsibility, and stewardship). 239; green care 97; "ex-ante responsibility" allowing the analysis of how collective capabilities and collective agency emerge from social interactions." responsibilities towards nature (206); reciprocity as key cultural and social values (Noorgard, Klamath River) 196; Pachamama: Reciprocity or ayni is the glue that holds everything together. 181; eudaemonic values in general - "values associated with living a good life as well as reflection about how preferences and societal choices relate to notions of justice, reciprocity, care and virtue" 163 ● civic environmentalism - developing a healths civic life that protects the integrity of ecosystems, species etc. ● justice, equity and self-determination ● habitus 136 ● Relational values as motivations based on feelings of connectedness to something larger than yourself and feelings of affection and care for the larger whole: ii ● inherent and embodied relations between mind, body, culture and environment 	
	<p>specific relationships</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assigned ● Variations on Chan et al: iiiii 'preferences, principles, and virtues associated with relationships, both interpersonal and as articulated by policies and social norms'; "Relational values are the preferences, principles, and virtues associated with relationships, as articulated by policies and social norms and are often intertwined with cultural ecosystem services" 159; "preferences, principles, and virtues associated with the relationships that people have with components of nature, i.e. when the relationships themselves matter to people, beyond a means to an end." 239 (broad or specific?); iii ● derivative of relationships and responsibilities to them; relations to landscapes; ● human's relations to the material dimension of our environment ● values relative to the meaningfulness of relationships ● held by individuals or groups of people in relation to specific qualities or features in the environment, including place-specific ones ● Meaningful and desirable relationships: "values of desirable relationships between people and nature and among people (through nature)" (239), value of relationships, the importance of nature to foster desirable relationships between people and nature; "RV reflect 	<p>44</p>

		<p>meaning-saturated relationships with nature (Chan et al. 2018). Such relationships meaningfully matter to people, and as such are not substitutable from the valuer's perspective (individually or collectively)." 239; "meaningful, non-substitutable relationships between people and their environment" 158 iiiiiiiii</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Eudaemonic (contribute to a meaningful life worth living 239; "relations that are constitutive of a good life, i.e. a life worthy of a human being, in which not merely surviving, but flourishing can be achieved" 143 iii • Fundamental (protecting life supporting systems and giving sense to people's existence 239 • non-use values ii, quantifiable (205) • observing nature; recreation and picnicking; historical and cultural values; education and science; local identity; spiritual values; border protection • kinship i, companionship ii • sense of pride - functional and spiritual connection to landscape • DOING/ partnership? Community involvement in protection, creation, maintenance and use of green spaces 156 • generates benefits for both parties of a relationship 149 • spiritual value: "spiritual value resides in those species, places, and qualities that shape our identity, community and, in a wider sense, our place and purpose in the universe" 114; does not exclude use, but implies respectful use. ii • "ways in which nature facilitates a good quality of life through the relationships people form with nature, and the responsibilities that arise from these relationships [...] context-dependent nature of relational values" 95 • NCP • "forest values which directly relate to people's functionings (people's beings and doings)" 92 	
	interactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • emerge from the interaction between subject and object • human-nature encounter - relationship to place (situativity of reason) influence values and beliefs • participation in nature 	
	identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • individual and community identity (our people) iiiiiiiiiiiiiii: identity and purpose (what do I do?) Noorgaard, Klamath River 196; crocodile important for Filipinos identity (261), mystic values; identification with landscapes - cultural landscapes; farmers "develop a respect for the wholeness, harmony or identity of a living entity, based on a personal involvement with the life of plants or animals." 265 • We and our body are part of the environment ... When you kill animals you have to know that they are part of the creation; we are not allowed to kill the animals that give us life, as it is not part of the continuation of the liberating work of Christ. 247 • "The landscape of any farm is the owner's portrait of himself (4)": iii • Implied that all values are part of identity • Cultural Identity • Individual Identity 	25
	care and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • care & stewardship iiiiiiiiiiiii; caring attitude towards wild, vulnerable animal in a free environment (termed as intrinsic); caring FOR; ""[We] 	27

	responsibility	<p>can have traditions if we respect the fish". The emphasis on traditions being possible only when people are respectful, suggests that some people perceive ecosystem quality (or quantity) as a result of good stewardship or correct behaviour or, in other words, hold normative judgements about the correct behaviour towards ecosystem services." 170; care for pets as part of family</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● responsibilities to the natural world and towards the community; moral responsibility for others iiiii ● partnership with nature i ● Meaningful relations and responsibilities between humans and between humans and nature (7): ii ● Reciprocity with nature: i ● Love resulting in care and responsibility for being or place (229, attributed to "intrinsic value") ● Derivative from relationships between people, people and nature, and responsibilities toward these relationships (235). ● Care and stewardship: i 	
	sense of place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● sense of place iiiiii ● community gardens for example ● connection to place ● Nature as home i ● Local perspectives and value of place (non-western/indigenous): i ● Place attachment influence on well-being: ii ● Connection to the "land" ● Relational values include/ reflect identity and responsibility but specific to place: i 	16
	health and wellbeing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● mental and physical health ● all aspects of wellbeing besides only provisioning services (instrumental) 	
	relationships in community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● landscapes important for communal relationships (socio-cultural) ● providers of connection among people iiiii ● RV support caring relationships for others 	
	nature's gift sacred	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● in ILK perspectives ii ● nature as sacred ● "The spiritual value of nature might be described as a relationship that we perceive between ourselves, other living creatures, and the physical environment" "Spiritual value is not inconsistent with use, but is inconsistent with depletion, extinction, waste, and disrespect" 114 	
	cultural values/ cultural ES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● the cultural importance of nature, which includes aesthetic, recreational, spiritual, scientific and psychological values" (but classified as instrumental) ● socio-cultural values iii ● Cultural ES iii ● Relational values closely associated with or synonymous to cultural values: ii 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "values relative to the meaningfulness of relationships, including the relationships between individuals or societies and other animals and 	

		<p>aspects of the lifeworld (all of who may be understood as conscious persons), as well as those among individuals and articulated by formal and informal institutions. Another type of relational values, eudaimonistic values are associated with a good life, which includes considerations of principles and virtues, and values the actions and habits that are conducive to a meaningful and satisfying life." (Pascual et al 2017)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Y, X may gain some protection under the auspices of the people of Y's legal right to their own cultural identity, if the following three criteria are met: 1 The people of Y have a meaningful relationship with X. 2 Were that relationship to disappear, the cultural identity of those people would be destabilised. 3 The people of Y have a legal right to their cultural identity" 140 	
	Eudemonic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eudemonic values, living a good life: iii 	
	Transformative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transformative value, capacity to change preferences in accordance to a higher ideal, associated with spiritual or aesthetic values. 	
	Non-Instrumental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • non-exchangeable, non-instrumental human benefits 	
	Fuzzy areas and overlaps with other value types	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gradients between different types of values (239) • reference to Leopold in intrinsic language but: "The human good that ethics is meant to identify and serve is the development of the whole person in the full intensity and extensiveness of his or her relationships. One of these relationships, perhaps the most crucial, is the one connecting us to the physical world." 125 • There is a value in sense of place, identity, community, etc. but the nature of that value is not explored or considered "relational value": i • Relational values as a connection between intrinsic and instrumental? • Kinship between species (tree of life/web of life) as basis for intrinsic value of other species may be a fuzzy area between intrinsic and relational values (225) • Related to aesthetic values, perhaps similar to "pleasure and awe" in intrinsic values above. • Ecological value may be a bridge to relational values from instrumental or intrinsic? • immediate value, non-instrumental and non intrinsic - use a third category because not all non-instrumental values are intrinsic • pluricentric ii • anthropocentric, non instrumental ii 	
	Relationships with Nature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ES concept "offers a way to reconceptualize humanity's relationship with nature. ES reflect human dependence on Earth's life-support system by including reciprocal feedbacks between humans and their environment" (240) 	
	Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implicitly implied in education towards relationships to nature and wonder 	
	boundary object	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RV convincing as a boundary object to use in decision making 	

	<p>Chinese traditions more relational</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interdependence that has become more relevant with the ecological crisis ● care and stewardship 	
<p>Interpretations and Questions</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● difficult to measure but important ● The importance of relationships between and within human and natural systems, context dependent: i ● Ways natural environments contribute to our cultural and social lives, including care and innate value of nature (8): i ● Relational values are a form of intrinsic values: i ● Relational values have aspects of instrumental and intrinsic values: iii ● Relational and intrinsic values can shape each other: i 	